

IMPROVING PROFESSIONAL LEGAL COMPETENCE OF TEACHERS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS.

Z.K.Mamazova

Teacher of the International Islamic Academy of Uzbekistan
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ABSTRACT: In this article, an important factor for improving the educational process is inextricably linked with the high level of professional legal competence of teachers of technological education in the higher education system. Therefore, it is determined that one of the urgent tasks is to create the theoretical and practical foundations of the process of forming the professional legal competence of teachers of technological education based on the effective use of the opportunities of modern educational technologies and the created educational methodological complexes. In this regard, it is an urgent task to scientifically substantiate new approaches that ensure the level of professional legal competence required from the period of training of teachers of technological education in a higher educational institution.

KEY WORDS: Competence, professional legal, basic competence, professional activity, daily relations, personality development, value, spiritual and moral.

УЛУЧШЕНИЕ ОФИЦИАЛЬНОГО ЮРИДИЧЕСКОГО СОРЕВНОВАНИЯ УЧИТЕЛЯ В ПРЕДЫДУЩИХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ПРОБЛЕМАХ.

АННОТАЦИЯ: В данной статье важный фактор совершенствования образовательного процесса связан с высоким уровнем формирования профессиональной правовой компетенции преподавателей технологического образования в системе высшего образования. Поэтому одним из актуальных задач является создание теоретических и практических основ процесса формирования профессиональной правовой компетенции преподавателей технологического образования на основе эффективного использования возможностей современных образовательных технологий и создаваемых учебных методических комплексов. В этой связи актуальной задачей становится научное обоснование новых подходов, обеспечивающих уровень профессиональной правовой компетентности, требуемый со времен подготовки преподавателей технологического образования в вузе.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: компетентность, профессиональное право, базовая компетентность, профессиональная деятельность, ежедневные отношения, развитие личности, ценность, духовно-этическая.

ACCESS:

One of the elements of the teacher's professional competence is legal competence, which is an important tool in the process of implementing the state policy on the formation of a high-level legal culture, as well as in the formation of citizens' sense of respect for the law. The importance of the teacher's role is that the legal consciousness of the young generation largely depends on the teacher, because he creates a special legal space for the development of the student's personality. "Today, any sphere of life, any profession works in a legal context,

therefore, specialists in any field of education should act adequately in the system of legal knowledge in order to use them optimally." during the reform process, the creation and development of a new continuous education system aimed at taking a worthy place in the world in the field of education was defined as a priority task. The implemented reforms are aimed, first of all, at the continuous improvement of the quality and efficiency of education in accordance with the progressive development of science and technology, the modernization of social relations in society, and the new demands of the state and social life as the main customer.

An important factor in improving the educational process is closely related to the high level of professional legal competence of teachers of technological education in the higher education system. Therefore, it is determined that one of the urgent tasks is to create the theoretical and practical foundations of the process of forming the professional legal competence of teachers of technological education based on the effective use of the opportunities of modern educational technologies and the created educational methodological complexes. In this regard, it is an urgent task to scientifically substantiate new approaches that ensure the level of professional legal competence required from the period of training of teachers of technological education in a higher educational institution.

A direct study of the content of education in practice in foreign countries regarding the professional training of specialists showed that in Western countries the main place is occupied by the level of competence of the specialist. The minimum requirements of the educational content of the national education system of our republic are based on knowledge, skills and qualifications. If we look at the etymological analysis of the concepts "competent" and "competence", we can understand that they did not arise by chance. Competence does not mean the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by the student, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction.

From the point of view of the requirements for the level of professional training of graduates, competence means the ability of students to use a set of knowledge, skills and activity methods appropriately in certain situations. Competence is expressed by the student's acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for the implementation of personal and socially significant professional activities and their ability to apply them in professional activities. In this place, the essence of the concept of "competence" is fully revealed, and it is manifested in the following two forms: competence as a set of personal qualities of students and basic requirements of the professional field.

Due to the fact that the educational content is grouped into blocks of subjects in the curriculum (for all subjects), interdisciplinary (for a set of subjects) and subjects (for a specific subject), we recognize the following three levels of competence : - basic competence (focus on humanitarian, socio-economic content of education); - interdisciplinary competence (according to the specific scope of educational subjects and educational blocks of general professional training); - competence in one subject (subject) (according to having a clear and certain opportunity within a special academic subject).

Thus, basic competence is determined at the level of educational blocks and academic subjects for each stage of higher pedagogical education. In determining the order of basic competence, the essence of social and personal experience in accordance with the main goals of professional pedagogical education, the main types that allow the acquisition of life skills in the process of organizing professional activity in social society are of great importance. From

this point of view, they are divided into the following types of competence:
Comprehensive competence.

It is related to the student's valuable orientations, his ability to feel and understand social existence, to find an independent way of life, to understand his role and place in social society, to set a clear goal in the organization of actions and to make a decision. reception competence, competence related to worldview, it provides a mechanism for self-determination for the student in educational and other situations. The student's individual educational direction and the general program of his life activities depend on this competence.

Socio-cultural competence. The scope of knowledge and activity experience that the student needs to master in depth is the characteristics of national and universal cultures, the spiritual and moral foundations of human and human life, the cultural foundations of family and social traditions, the role of science and religion in human life. , their impact on material existence, knowledge about life and recreation, for example, knowing how to effectively organize free time.

Educational competence is a set of independent thinking competences, which consists of elements of logical, methodological and social activities of the student related to specific objects of study, including the ability to see the goal, plan activities , includes knowledge and skills in analyzing its content, reflection, personal assessment of activity. In relation to the studied objects, students acquire creative skills, that is, obtaining knowledge directly from existence, methods of action and heuristic methods of solving problems in non-standard situations. Information acquisition competence. With the help of audio-video tools and information technologies, the ability to independently search, analyze and select the necessary information, change it, store and transmit it is formed.

This competence ensures that the student learns the basics of academic subjects on the basis of important information. Communicative competence. It includes interaction with students, their methods, mastering the language that takes priority in the communication process, skills of working in groups, organizing and conducting various spiritual and educational events in the team. Social-active competence includes citizenship (citizen, observer, voter, representative), social work (consumer, buyer, client, producer rights), family relations and obligations, economic and legal issues, professional, as well as personal It means acquiring knowledge and experience in determining one's position (in particular, analyzing the current situation in the labor market, the ability to act in pursuit of personal and social interests, and knowledge of the etiquette of labor and civil relations).

Competence related to practical activity means the ability to move from one state of action to another, to apply actions and actions in new situations, and to quickly find direction in new information. It is appropriate to consider the normative model of training a specialist, which includes educational and cognitive activities for acquiring a future profession. It is expressed in the qualification characteristics of a graduate of a higher education institution of the relevant direction and level of training, and scientifically based knowledge, skills and qualifications reflect the composition of the important professional qualities of a person.

In particular, a graduate of a higher educational institution with a teacher's qualification in the field of technological education: readiness to conduct pedagogical activities in accordance with the requirements of state educational standards, a high level of theoretical and practical training to use modern teaching technologies, to participate in the development

of educational programs, to be responsible for their full implementation in accordance with the curriculum and educational process, the knowledge and skills of learners and organize control of their qualifications, prepare them to use the acquired knowledge in practical activities and control the independent work of learners, create a basis for the teaching and methodical equipment of specific educational subjects; to participate in the scientific and methodical activities of the educational institution, to perform the duties of a class leader, to organize and conduct educational work with students, to ensure the implementation of educational plans and programs, to ensure educational discipline, It is necessary to observe the rights and freedoms of the students, to improve their professional qualifications.

In the qualification description of the specialist, the content of the training of bachelors in the field of education is expressed mainly by the active-creative aspect of the future teacher's knowledge, and it implies the experience of comprehensively solving the professional tasks of secondary special vocational education. Based on the understanding that professional legal competence is based on the reflection of the specialist's activity and the important characteristics of its internal structure, the structure of professional legal competence can be clarified in terms of describing its main components. In relation to pedagogical activity, the approach of separating its components as relatively independent functional types of pedagogic activity prevails. According to the point of view of V.A. Slastenin, the training of a pedagogue involves the education of the knowledge of performing these tasks: analytical-reflexive, constructive-prognostic, organizational, evaluation-information, correction-verification.

The point of view taken by the author, in our opinion, largely reflects the established ideas about the structure of the teacher's activity. At the same time, the research of the structure of the future specialist's professional competence is a thorough analysis of the pedagogue's work, the level of his training is currently being modernized and the concept of continuous pedagogical education is being implemented by the system of higher and secondary special vocational education. means determining the requirements. Such a setting of the problem requires a different approach to tools, methods, and the knowledge of the teacher who is carrying out the education of a certain type of activity in the student.

B. Djurayeva's opinion is largely compatible with the implementation of the active approach: she distinguishes these types of teacher activity: gnostic, educational-methodical, creative, communicative-organizational. The following are structural elements of pedagogical activity: Integrating the content of knowledge relevant to this subject into the structure of typical issues of the specialist's professional activity.

Developing and classifying the goals of teaching a subject. Selection of the educational and methodological content of the subject and dissemination of the teaching program according to the elements of students' cognitive activities. Creative activity - development of educational and methodological support in accordance with the curriculum on all selected topics. Development of communicative and organizational aspects of student-teacher interaction in the process of self-directed work of students. Organization of corrective control. Constructive and design components of the activity were included by the author in the composition of the gnostic element.

At the same time, it is suggested to consider the creative and communicative-organizational components of the teacher's activity as independent components. In this approach, attention

is focused on the need to organize interaction between teachers and students in the course of self-directed learning activities of students. These types of activities are completely and fully implemented by the teacher in the design, construction and implementation of vocationally oriented teaching technology. Professional legal competence of teachers is manifested in all aspects of pedagogical work: professional activity, daily relationships, personality development, the collective result of work and requires the formation of all its components. It should be noted that the most important task of a teacher of higher educational institutions is to create psychological and pedagogical conditions for the gradual education of students' ability to stabilize, fill and manage transfer mechanisms.

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